

2 **Effects of mooring compliancy on the mooring forces,** 3 **power production and dynamics of a floating wave** 4 **activated body energy converter – Supplementary** 5 **material**

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10 **Abstract:** This section presents a few tables of results associated to the paper published by
11 Energies, with title given above.

12 **Keywords:** wave energy converter; mooring compliancy; CALM mooring system
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14 **Numerical modeling of moorings in deep waters**

15 *Short description of the numerical model*

16 Numerical simulations were performed with the code ANSYS-AQWA (version 15.0),
17 developed by ANSYS. Details are given in the main paper.

18 *Output of the mooring schemes*

19 Three CALM mooring schemes were designed and investigated. In each scheme, the device is
20 linked to a front catenary moored buoy. The schemes were simulated under several ordinary and
21 extreme WSs (WSs n. 4, 6, 7, 10, 11, see main paper) with different wave obliquities (i.e. 0°, 20°, 40°,
22 60°). In particular, extreme WSs aimed at the selection of the mooring chains, whereas ordinary
23 WSs aimed at achieving information on the device movements, and hence, indirectly, on the power
24 production.

25 The plan view of the three schemes and the characteristics of the mooring chains are also given
26 in the main paper.

27 The results of the numerical simulations are reported below in terms of: i) forces acting on the
28 mooring lines, ii) surge movements (amplitudes of the oscillations), and iii) the pitch movements
29 which are correlated to the device power production.

30 The results correspond to the statistical values of the times histories representing the mean
31 value of the upper 10% for the displacements and of the upper 2% for the forces (to characterise the
32 extreme force F1/50).

33 The forces on the mooring lines and the surge movements for each body composing the
34 mooring scheme are reported in Tables 1 to 6.
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Table 1 – Forces acting on the mooring lines of the first mooring scheme. Values are in kN.

	$\beta=0^\circ$					$\beta=20^\circ$					$\beta=40^\circ$				$\beta=60^\circ$					
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
Chain 1a	352	474	619	626	890	342	448	586	549	610	331	423	914	517	618	312	359	535	639	749
Chain 2a	58	64	68	65	164	56	59	63	91	104	54	57	184	82	191	48	57	63	137	157
Chain 3a	19	21	23	25	37	18	20	22	24	34	18	20	23	24	48	18	19	24	23	31
Chain 4a	58	64	68	65	157	60	70	99	103	182	71	87	213	201	239	97	142	296	288	480
Cable	187	239	310	336	370	183	232	313	311	316	188	229	807	283	320	199	227	401	542	454
Rear chain	181	248	463	825	881	177	237	508	703	835	187	266	1359	485	592	230	267	595	1314	961

Table 2 Surge movements of the different parts, for the first mooring scheme. Values are in m.

	$\beta=0^\circ$					$\beta=20^\circ$					$\beta=40^\circ$					$\beta=60^\circ$				
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
Buoy	3.07	4.66	5.50	6.52	6.49	2.91	4.46	5.17	5.64	5.81	2.76	4.10	5.21	5.52	5.32	2.71	3.05	4.28	4.75	4.06
Front	1.80	3.10	7.16	8.55	8.13	1.48	3.08	7.32	7.82	7.89	1.86	3.93	16.34	5.77	7.61	2.34	2.73	7.09	9.61	9.25
Rear	1.81	3.16	7.24	8.61	8.11	1.52	3.15	7.41	7.89	7.93	1.86	3.99	16.60	5.85	7.42	2.29	2.87	6.82	7.76	8.01

Table 3 – Forces acting on the mooring lines of the second mooring scheme. Values are in kN.

	$\beta= 0^\circ$					$\beta= 20^\circ$			$\beta= 40^\circ$					$\beta= 60^\circ$						
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
Chain 1b	159	213	283	289	319	167	216	331	332	340	210	239	429	395	419	216	286	506	379	563
Chain 2b	159	213	285	289	320	151	203	295	301	357	131	202	213	317	299	115	141	400	221	782
Chain 3b	43	47	52	51	57	42	45	54	60	53	39	48	54	61	61	37	38	60	68	124
Chain 4b	21	23	26	27	28	21	23	28	25	24	20	23	28	25	26	20	21	28	27	37
Chain 5b	18	19	22	24	23	17	19	24	22	21	18	20	24	23	23	17	19	24	21	22
Chain 6b	18	19	22	24	23	17	19	24	25	26	18	21	26	28	29	18	21	26	27	28
Chain 7b	21	24	26	27	28	21	24	31	34	39	23	32	39	49	48	26	36	48	52	60
Chain 8b	43	47	52	51	57	47	50	70	72	84	50	68	103	125	114	64	92	188	171	321
Cable	184	231	297	320	343	182	218	297	303	321	184	211	280	373	389	194	246	623	433	908
Rear chain	176	215	448	827	912	163	214	503	702	748	182	267	483	811	996	230	334	462	946	1559

Table 4– Surge movements of the different parts, for the second mooring scheme. Values are in m.

	$\beta= 0^\circ$					$\beta= 20^\circ$					$\beta= 40^\circ$					$\beta= 60^\circ$				
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
Buoy	3.0	4.4	5.4	6.38	6.98	2.87	4.07	5.02	5.86	6.28	2.68	3.91	5.04	5.59	5.59	2.79	3.28	4.55	4.66	5.01
Front	1.5	2.8	7.1	8.43	8.69	1.01	2.79	7.32	7.84	7.59	1.63	3.85	6.00	9.50	9.46	2.59	3.59	11.86	7.37	16.13
Rear	1.5	2.9	7.2	8.49	8.71	1.04	2.85	7.41	7.95	7.72	1.67	3.94	6.03	9.29	9.32	2.49	3.89	11.42	6.02	12.93

Table 5 – Forces acting on the mooring lines of the third mooring scheme. Values are in kN.

	$\beta= 0^\circ$					$\beta= 20^\circ$					$\beta= 40^\circ$					$\beta= 60^\circ$				
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
1b	32	43	67	64	70	39	45	69	74	74	79	91	165	161	158	270	335	620	432	710
2b	176	217	336	328	352	143	160	277	264	313	172	297	289	496	427	231	314	863	529	1740
3b	268	278	333	311	350	339	434	477	552	467	318	379	461	546	534	604	696	1083	1233	2094
4b	55	54	63	61	70	91	91	113	98	104	232	271	306	268	299	1185	1061	1526	1363	2052
5b	46	52	62	62	0	48	52	61	57	0	50	50	68	58	0	40	50	70	49	0
6b	47	50	53	66	0	45	51	61	61	0	50	54	73	74	0	45	60	73	63	0
7b	57	62	61	61	0	54	56	83	85	0	52	81	106	119	0	62	89	123	141	0
8b	260	289	289	300	0	308	327	464	477	0	291	444	686	801	0	362	596	1249	961	0
Cable	160	211	291	273	310	169	219	298	297	294	157	174	237	320	355	392	483	1389	986	1882
9c	139	157	203	215	242	110	127	150	178	179	76	97	125	156	167	1582	1789	5219	3712	7211
10c	55	62	82	97	102	96	115	147	166	174	107	108	173	200	222	977	1287	3557	2111	4878
11c	57	73	87	101	100	105	129	164	176	176	115	138	186	233	238	1196	1704	4645	3080	6167
12c	15	21	24	26	30	57	68	95	97	111	48	58	81	96	106	96	115	314	210	431

Table 6 Surge movements of the different parts, for the third mooring scheme. Values are in m.

	$\beta= 0^\circ$					$\beta= 20^\circ$					$\beta= 40^\circ$					$\beta= 60^\circ$				
	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11	WS 4	WS 6	WS 7	WS 10	WS 11
Buoy	4.5	6.2	8.5	9.4	10.6	18.2	14.6	7.9	9.7	11.7	3.1	4.4	6.1	7.1	6.5	2.9	3.2	4.7	4.2	4.9
Front	2.5	4.8	12.6	14.4	14.7	6.1	8.7	11.2	14.1	14.1	1.7	4.2	6.6	10.9	11.1	2.4	3.8	12.9	15.6	16.1
Rear	2.1	4.3	10.1	13.3	13.3	6.4	9.1	11.5	14.5	14.4	1.9	4.7	7.2	10.7	10.9	2.6	3.8	12.1	13.2	15.7
Rear buoy	1.7	3.5	7.9	9.7	10.1	4.9	7.7	8.9	10.2	10.9	1.6	3.5	5.6	8.2	8.3	1.9	2.9	8.6	11.3	12.0

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